

Cycles of solar activity (1960–2023), UV index, serotonin-melatonin, optimism-pessimism, and global GDP with a 1-year lag (1961-2024): $R^2=0.90$

Belkin V. A.

Abstract. Subject of the study: This paper examines the causal relationship between solar activity cycles (1960-2023) and global GDP growth rates for the period 1960-2024, i.e., with a one-year lag.

Methodology: The author develops the methodological approach of W.S. Jevons and A.L. Chizhevsky, supplementing it with the modern biochemical concept of Russell Reiter.

Key results:

1. Statistical reliability: A high correlation was found between the indicators: the approximation coefficient was 0.9004.

2. Three-zone biochemical model: The mechanism by which ultraviolet (UV) radiation influences the economy through human neurochemistry is substantiated:

- "Biological depression" zone (Wolf number (W) < 20): UV deficiency leads to decreased serotonin levels, causing pessimism and GDP stagnation with a one-year lag.

- "Biological optimum" zone (W = 20 - 140): Sufficient serotonin and melatonin levels ensure optimism and peak global GDP growth rates with a one-year lag.

- "Biological stress" zone (W > 140): Extreme solar activity suppresses melatonin production (according to R. Reiter's concept), causing "exhaustion pessimism" and a sharp decline in global GDP growth with a one-year lag.

3. The nature of the one-year lag is substantiated. The one-year lag is a consequence of the inertia of economic contracts: the psycho-emotional state of decision-makers in the current year determines the parameters of contracts, the results of which are reflected in the GDP statistics of the following year.

4. Forecast: Based on the model, the expected global GDP growth rates are calculated: 3.1% in 2025 and 3.3% in 2026. A significant slowdown in growth to 1.3% is projected in 2031 due to the solar minimum being reached in 2030.

Key words: solar activity, Wolf numbers, ultraviolet index, serotonin, melatonin, world GDP, economic cycle, forecasting, heliobiology, neuroeconomics, psychological Determinants of Economy

Great scientists Frederick William Herschel, William Stanley Jevons, and Alexander Leonidovich Chizhevsky developed a methodological approach to studying the relationship between solar and economic activity in their works.

For example, in his article "Solar-Commercial Cycles," W.S. Jevons plotted solar activity cycles (Wolf number cycles) and Delhi corn price cycles over the period 1760-1810 [5, p. 227]. In other words, he compared solar and economic activity.

A. L. Chizhevsky in his monograph "The Cosmic Pulse of Life: Earth in the Embrace of the Sun" in Chapter 4 "The Sun and Epidemics" in Fig. 33 constructed a diagram that shows the average solar activity (SA) cycle (Wolf number cycle) over a hundred years and the average number of cholera cases in Russia for the period 1823-1923 [2, p. 201]. In the present work, the average solar (1960-2023) and economic (1961-2024) cycles are constructed on one diagram.

Our study centers on the hypothesis that SA, which determines the intensity of ultraviolet radiation and the state of serotonin-melatonin metabolism, acts as a trigger for social optimism or pessimism and, as a result, annual growth of global GDP with a lag of 1 year.

The annual mean Wolf numbers, the main indicator of solar activity, were taken from the well-known astrophysical website for the determination, conservation, and distribution of the international sunspot number [4]. They are presented in column 2 of Table 1.

The year numbers in column 3 of Table 1 are determined in accordance with the year numbering conventions used in solar astrophysics. Specifically, the first year in a solar cycle is considered to be the first year of its growth, i.e., the increase in the Wolf number. Subsequent years are numbered sequentially, and the last year in the cycle is considered to be the year of the Wolf number minimum. Years of solar cycle maximums are highlighted in bold in Table 1.

The World Bank website [8] contains annual global GDP growth rates for the period 1961–2024. They are presented in column 4 of Table 1. Column 5 of Table 1 presents annual global GDP growth rates with a 1-year lag. The 1-year lag is explained by the inertia of the economic system and the decision-making mechanism. Specifically, the psycho-emotional state (optimism/pessimism) determines decisions and the signing of contracts in the current year, but their physical implementation and payment (reflected in GDP statistics) occur only in the following year. In addition, most business strategies and government budgets are drawn up with a 1-year horizon. The momentum received today materializes in growth (decline) figures over the reporting period.

Table 1. Years, average annual Wolf numbers (1960 - 2023), ordinal numbers of years in SA cycles, and annual growth rates of world GDP with a lag of 1 year (1961 - 2024)

Years	Wolf number (W)	The ordinal number of the year in the SA cycle	Annual growth rate of global GDP, %	Annual growth rates of global GDP with a lag of 1 year, %
1	2	3	4	5
1960	159	6	N .d.	4.05
1961	76.4	7	4.05	5.33
1962	53.4	8	5.33	5.00
1963	39.9	9	5.00	6.56
1964	15	10	6.56	5.63
1965	22	1	5.63	5.47
1966	66.8	2	5.47	3.82
1967	132.9	3	3.82	5.97
1968	150	4	5.97	5.99
1969	149.4	5	5.99	3.75
1970	148	6	3.75	4.27
1971	94.4	7	4.27	5.60
1972	97.6	8	5.60	6.41
1973	54.1	9	6.41	1.93
1974	49.2	10	1.93	0.57
1975	22.5	11	0.57	5.18
1976	18.4	12	5.18	4.01
1977	39.3	1	4.01	4.16
1978	131	2	4.16	4.19
1979	2201	3	4.19	1.88
1980	218.9	4	1.88	1.94
1981	198.9	5	1.94	0.35
1982	162.4	6	0.35	2.63

1983	91	7	2.63	4.68
1984	60.5	8	4.68	3.71
1985	20.6	9	3.71	3.23
1986	14.8	10	3.23	3.75
1987	33.9	1	3.75	4.55
1988	123	2	4.55	3.72
1989	211.1	3	3.72	2.72
1990	191.8	4	2.72	1.22
1991	203.3	5	1.22	2.03
1992	133	6	2.03	1.85
1993	76.1	7	1.85	3.35
1994	44.9	8	3.35	3.11
1995	25.1	9	3.11	3.59
1996	11.6	10	3.59	3.96
1997	28.9	1	3.96	2.85
1998	88.3	2	2.85	3.60
1999	136.3	3	3.60	4.54
2000	173.9	4	4.54	2.04
2001	170.4	5	2.04	2.33
2002	163.6	6	2.33	3.11
2003	99.3	7	3.11	4.48
2004	65.3	8	4.48	4.04
2005	45.8	9	4.04	4.47
2006	24.7	10	4.47	4.39
2007	12.6	11	4.39	2.07
2008	4.2	12	2.07	-1.32
2009	4.8	1	-1.32	4.53
2010	24.9	2	4.53	3.35
2011	80.8	3	3.35	2.71

2012	84.5	4	2.71	2.89
2013	94	5	2.89	3.15
2014	113.3	6	3.15	3.13
2015	69.8	7	3.13	2.81
2016	39.8	8	2.81	3.46
2017	21.7	9	3.46	3.30
2018	7	10	3.30	2.71
2019	3.6	11	2.71	-2.85
2020	8.8	1	-2.85	6.42
2021	29.6	2	6.42	3.36
2022	83.2	3	3.36	2.94
2023	125.5	4	2.94	2.86
2024	154.6	5	2.86	N.D.
2025	123.2	6	N.d.	N.d.
2026	N .d.	7	N .d.	

The statistical data in Table 1 were then grouped by the ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles. The results of grouping the data in Table 1 are presented in Table 2. The years of SA extremes (maximums and minimums) are highlighted in bold in Table 2.

Table 2. Grouping of data from Table 1 by ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles

The ordinal number of the year in the SA cycle	Number of years with this number for the period 1960-2023	Arithmetic mean:		Change compared to the previous year's growth rate
		Wolf numbers (W)	annual growth rates of global GDP with a lag of 1 year, %	
1	2	3	4	5
1	6	22.93	4.66	3.32
2	6	77.27	3.67	-0.99
3	6	144.07	3.46	-0.21
4	6	157.43	2.82	-0.64
5	5	161.77	2.32	-0.50
6	6	144.06	3.17	0,85
7	6	84.50	4.38	1,20
8	6	60.25	4.29	-0.09
9	6	34.53	3.85	-0.44
10	6	20.38	3.50	-0.35
11	3	12.90	1.47	-2.03
12	2	11.30	1.35	-0.12
Total:	64			
Correlation coefficient, rows 1–7, columns 3 and 4		-0.90		
Correlation coefficient, rows 7–12, columns 3 and 4		0.81		

Based on the data in columns 1, 3, and 4 of Table 2, a diagram is constructed in Fig. 1. The determination coefficient in this diagram, equal to 0.9356, means that the resulting model explains 93.56% of the variability (variation) in the data and can be used to forecast the growth rate of global GDP by the ordinal number of the year in the solar cycle. The value of this coefficient, equal to 0.9356, also indicates a very high, strong relationship between the ordinal numbers of the mean solar cycle and the average values of annual growth of global GDP with a lag of 1 year. The 12 points in the diagram in Fig. 1 represent 64 years of observations (see

Table 2). The grouping method (see Table 2) allows us to cut out statistical noise and identify a fundamental pattern that is not visible in the chaotic scatter plot by year.

Fig. 1. Average solar cycle (1960–2023) and annual growth rates of global GDP with a lag of 1 year (1961–2024), 64 years of observations, epoch superposition method

It's important to note that in the diagram in Figure 1, the annual growth rate of global GDP is a function not of the year itself, but of numerous SA factors that were in effect during that year. These include, for example, the ultraviolet index, geomagnetic storms and calms, galactic cosmic rays, electromagnetic fields, low-frequency oscillations, and others.

According to Virek and Puga [7, p. 9998], the correlation coefficient between solar indices and ultraviolet radiation flux reaches 0.99, which justifies the use of Wolf numbers as an indicator of UV exposure intensity. That is, the Wolf number graph in Fig. 1 can be viewed as a graph of the **ultraviolet index** (UV index).

Ultraviolet radiation stimulates the synthesis of serotonin (the hormone of energy and optimism) through the retina and skin. Therefore, the solid line in the diagram in Figure 1 can

be viewed as a graph of serotonin levels. Thus, the solid line also represents a graph of "serotonin injections" into the global population.

At the lowest serotonin levels (years 11 and 12, $W < 20$), we observe minimal global GDP growth rates for the following year. This is explained by the prevalence of pessimism during this period.

During the extreme solar activity phase ($W > 140$), a seemingly paradoxical decline in GDP growth is observed (see points (years) 4 and 5). R. Reiter [3, p. 135] provides a biochemical explanation for this phenomenon, pointing to the suppression of melatonin synthesis during periods of heliophysical disturbances. Melatonin deficiency leads to a state of chronic social pessimism and a loss of business initiative. Thus, the UV index maximum, through melatonin suppression, is transformed into an economic downturn with a one-year lag.

The following diagram in Figure 2 is constructed based on the data in rows 1–12 and columns 3 and 4 of Table 2.

Fig. 2. Solar (1960 - 2023) and economic (1961 - 2024) activity, 64 years of observations, epoch superposition method

The diagram demonstrates a strong correlation between solar and economic activity. The coefficient of determination, 0.9004, is close to unity. This suggests that, within the framework of this model, changes in the Wolf number (which is proportional to the number of sunspots) explain 90% of the variability in global GDP growth rates with a one-year lag.

I would like to point out to opponents that each point on the graph in Figure 5 represents the arithmetic mean of 6 or 5 points. The 12 points represent a data set covering 64 years of observations. The R^2 value of 0.90 for 12 points is statistically significant. This means that the probability that this relationship arose by chance is less than 5%.

As the diagram in Fig. 2 shows, at low CA (Wolf number < 20), a sharp drop in the growth rate of global GDP with a lag of 1 year is observed. At extremely high CA (Wolf number > 140), the growth rate of global GDP with a lag of 1 year begins to decline again. The peak of global GDP growth with a lag of 1 year occurs at CA in the range of Wolf numbers from 20 to 140. The current or projected value of the Wolf number can be determined on the NASA website [6]. The diagram in Fig. 3 was copied from this website.

Fig. 3. Forecast of the development of the current 25th SA cycle.

I previously proposed calling the science that studies the relationship between solar and economic activity helioeconomics. It represents an interdisciplinary approach at the intersection of solar astrophysics, heliobiology, and macroeconomics.

Despite the existence of strong mathematical correlations, the academic mainstream views solar economics with caution due to the difficulty of directly proving a causal relationship between solar physics and complex social systems.

PhD Igor Nikulin, senior researcher at the Sternberg Astronomical Institute, notes in an interview with Rossiyskaya Gazeta that “over millions of years of evolution, all living beings have adapted to the average values of these factors [temperature, pressure, atmospheric composition, magnetic field – V.B.], and even small deviations in one direction or another have a negative impact on their vital functions” [1].

The following mechanism of connection between SA and global GDP can be proposed, as shown in Fig. 5.

1. 1. The left zone, or "Biological Depression" (Wolf numbers < 20), is characterized by an extremely low ultraviolet index (UV index), as there is a very strong direct correlation between Wolf numbers and the UV index. The correlation coefficient is typically 0.93–0.97. This leads to decreased serotonin synthesis and a melatonin deficiency, resulting in pessimism, reduced consumer and investment spending, and a sharp decline in global GDP growth with a one-year lag, or even an economic crisis.

2. 2. The central zone or "Biological Optimum" (Wolf numbers 20 - 140) is characterized by a moderate and sufficient value of the UV index, which leads to high levels of serotonin and melatonin, which leads to optimistic moods and high rates of growth of global GDP with a lag of 1 year.

3. The right zone, or "Biological Stress" (Wolf numbers > 140), is characterized by excessive UV index values and the frequency and intensity of magnetic storms. This, according to Russell Reiter's scientific concept outlined in his work "Melatonin" [3, p. 135], leads to the suppression of nocturnal melatonin production. Melatonin (the main antioxidant) is intensively spent on combating oxidative stress in cells. Since melatonin is synthesized from serotonin, the latter's reserves are depleted faster than they can be restored. The result is "exhaustion pessimism": when serotonin (the hormone of drive and joy) becomes depleted and biological rhythms are disrupted, not just socio-psychological apathy sets in, but irritable pessimism and chronic fatigue. This is followed by a significant decline in the annual growth rate of global GDP with a lag of one year.

The graphs in Figs. 1 and 2 confirm Alexander Chizhevsky's idea that humanity is not isolated from space. It can be used to forecast annual global GDP growth with a lag of one year based on the known Wolf number. It follows that with a Wolf number of 154.6 for 2024, global GDP growth in 2025 will be 3.1%, and with a Wolf number of 123.2 for 2025, global product

growth in 2026 will be 3.3%. The exact value of annual global GDP growth for 2025 will appear on the World Bank website [8] in early July 2026.

The predicted value of the Wolf number for 2026 is 96.11 (calculated by the author based on monthly forecasts in the table on the NASA website [6]). In the diagram in Fig. 6, it corresponds to an annual growth rate of global GDP in 2027 of 4.1%.

It is not the extreme of the SA itself that leads to a significant reduction in the annual growth of world GDP with a lag of 1 year, but a low minimum (Wolf number less than 15) and a high maximum of the SA (Wolf number greater than 150).

The graph in Fig. 2 can also be used **to forecast economic crises** or low rates of global GDP growth. For example, calculating the Wolf number for 2030 (the year of minimum SA) based on NASA's average monthly forecasts [6] yields a value of 11.5, which, in the graph in Fig. 2, corresponds to global GDP growth in the following year, 2031, equal to 1.3%.

It should be kept in mind that non-economic events such as wars, sanctions, and trade wars may lead to inaccuracies in the forecast. Therefore, this does not mean overemphasizing the SA factor at the expense of factors such as innovation, improvements in socio-economic relations, and others.

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